

THE JOINT TACTICAL RADIO AND THE NAVY RF DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM CHALLENGE

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ABSTRACT

In the area of communications on surface ships, the U.S. Navy is faced with many goals some of which conflict with each other. These goals include 1) Increasing communications capabilities, 2) Reducing manpower, 3) Reducing life-cycle costs, and 4) Reducing the number of antennas. Increasing communications capability while reducing manpower implies a significant increase in automation of these systems. The reduction of life-cycle costs often implies standardization of systems and the opening of production of replacement subsystems to many competing firms. Reducing the number of antennas is important for reducing weight and moment of ships, increasing the amount of mission-critical supplies, and reducing the radar cross section.

In an effort to increase communications capability while decreasing life-cycle costs, the U.S. Navy has recently begun procurement of the Digital Modular Radio (DMR), one of the first communications systems to address the requirements under the Joint Tactical Radio System (JTRS). Radios procured in the future must conform to the requirements under the JTRS. These requirements include open architecture, software programmability, use of commercial-off-the-shelf technology, and the ability to transmit or receive at any frequency between 2 MHz and 2.5 GHz. Line of sight communications such as ship-to-ship, ship-to-plane, or ship-to-shore, usually occur in the 30 to 400 MHz

frequency range. The wide scale deployment of a JTRS compliant radio is one factor in the need for an advanced RF distribution system.

Reducing the number of antennas while increasing communications capabilities presents significant new challenges in the area of electromagnetic interference (EMI). The requirement to reduce EMI is probably the most significant factor in the need for an advanced RF distribution system. Increasing number of radios must be coupled to the same antenna. Unless the signals from the multiple radios are shielded from each other, range of communications will be degraded due to increasing error rates and saturation of receivers. Each aspect is significantly worsened by the use of frequency-hopping radios. Also, in the extremely limited space on a ship, each antenna will interfere with many others in the same frequency range. One approach to reducing the EMI is an interference mitigation system that taps off some of the transmitted signal, changes its phase by a known amount, and adds it to that at the receive antenna.

An advanced RF distribution system is needed to accommodate JTRS compliant systems on U.S. Navy ships. On the transmit side such a system must take the broadband signal from the JTRS, amplify it by 30 dB, mitigate the effect from other transmissions, and route this signal to the appropriate antenna for efficient operation. On the receive side the distribution system must receive an extremely small signal, amplify it, and shield it from the effects of high power

transmissions from other antennas. There should be a high degree of automation and standardization of components. At a minimum the distribution system should accommodate the spectrum of line of sight communications for the JTRS. This is a significant challenge in the area of communications for the U.S. Navy in the twenty-first century.

INTRODUCTION

The transmission of information has always been critically important to military operations. The means of communication has become so powerful in recent times that the U.S. Navy has found it difficult to accommodate new capabilities in the design of ships. Compounding the problem is the fact that the U.S. Navy is faced with many design goals whose solution conflict with each other. The accommodation of new communications capabilities must be balanced against goals to reduce manpower, reduce life-cycle costs, and minimize the number of antennas on a ship. Higher data rates, greater diversity of information exchange, and increasing reliability are always the goals of military organizations. There is the need for the ship to report the local situation to headquarters and for the headquarters to report the global situation to the ship. There is the increasing need for ships to coordinate their activities with other ships and deployed aircraft, helicopters, vehicles, and dismounted troops on shore.

There is a goal to reduce manpower on ships. This goal is driven by both the desires to put fewer sailors in harm's way and to reduce costs. Reducing manpower often requires increasing automation.

Reducing total life-cycle costs has been a goal of the Department of Defense for many years. The initial cost of an electronic system is often a small portion of the entire amount of money spent for training, spare parts, maintenance, repairs, and upgrades. The present generation sometimes pays dearly for the decisions made on equipment twenty years previously. One method to reduce the total cost is to open the replacement and upgrade of equipment to competition. The architecture of the communications system must be open in the sense that the interface between components is publicly known and not proprietary to any organization. Companies

other than the original vendor must be able to provide for these replacements. Use of commercial off-the-shelf technology allows the incorporation of the benefits of the rapid development of communications equipment.

Minimizing the number of antennas is important because of their effect upon total weight and moment. Each pound placed above the center of gravity requires a corresponding increase in weight below (up to a factor of 5) to preserve stability. This affects the total amount of mission-critical supplies. Antennas also serve to affect the radar cross section of the ship. There is also a fierce competition for real estate especially at the highest point on the ship.

THE JOINT TACTICAL RADIO

In an attempt to solve some of the issues associated with the first three goals described above, the Department of Defense has issued an Operational Requirements Document (ORD) for the Joint Tactical Radio System (JTRS). The JTRS ORD specifies that all future communications systems in the 2 MHz to 2.5 GHz frequency band must satisfy new requirements.

The requirements of the JTRS ORD include open architecture, software programmability, interoperability, and capabilities to transmit or receive at any frequency between 2 MHz and 2.5 GHz. The software programmability of waveforms is an admission that the future is uncertain. New technology and new waveforms will arise that prove very beneficial. Programmability of the waveform provides for flexibility and allows new types of signals to be transmitted after reading a file from a disk. Such software programmability should also reduce the total lifetime cost of the system. There will be less spent on training, storing, and procuring spare parts for many different systems.

The Navy has begun limited procurement of the Digital Modular Radio (DMR), the first system that attempts to satisfy the requirements of the JTRS ORD. Development of the DMR started well before consideration of the JTRS ORD. The DMR is software programmable and supports the following waveforms: satellite communications in the band (244 to 270 MHz for receive or downlink and 294 to 317 MHz for transmit or uplink), SINCGARS (30 to 88 MHz), Have Quick and UHF Line of Sight (225 to 400

MHz), and Link 4A, and 11. The number of channels of each type of signal depends upon the class of ship. A power amplifier that adds 30 dB to the signal is part of the procurement of the DMR. The 30 to 400 MHz band is the primary one for line-of-sight communications on U.S. Navy ships.

ELECTROMAGNETIC INTERFERENCE

On a platform with very limited space such as a surface ship, electromagnetic interference is one of the primary limitations to any increase in communications capabilities. Each new system that the Navy would like to install usually requires a new antenna. The new antenna if transmitting high power signals interferes with many of the existing receiving ones. The existing high-power transmitters including radars, in turn, interfere with the new receiving antenna. The use of frequency-hopping systems greatly increases the amount of electromagnetic interference.

For such systems there are seven primary interactions that must be considered. They are:

- Receiver adjacent signal effects: non co-channel signals close in frequency to the desired signal but outside the nominal pass band of the receiver
- Transmitter broadband noise: emissions outside the band containing desired modulation components.
- Narrowband transmitter spurious emissions: discrete narrow band emissions generated by oscillators or power amplifiers in the transmitter circuit.
- Receiver spurious responses: intermodulation response between one external interfering signal and one internally generated signal source, usually a local oscillator.
- Receiver intermodulation: signals from two or more transmitters that enter a receiver and combine in the circuitry to produce signals at other frequency mixes.
- Transmitter intermodulation: an undesired signal that enters the input or output of the transmitter to combine with the desired signal to produce sum and difference frequencies.

- Co-channel effects: interactions, which occasionally occur in frequency-hopping systems when transmitters and receivers use overlapping hopsets.

One of the primary effects of a transmitter of high power is to saturate the receiver. The range of communications is then often severely limited. The bit-error rate increases significantly and the bandwidth and data rate decrease. Usually no more than four frequency-hopping systems can operate simultaneously in the same general area.

Two of the purposes of a signal distribution system are to limit the effects of electromagnetic interference and to put multiple signals on one antenna. A device to accomplish these purposes is called a multicoupler. The multicoupler filters the signals, greatly decreases mutual interactions, and applies the signals to one antenna. Currently, the Navy uses a multicoupler in the 30 to 88 MHz frequency band to accommodate the frequency hopping SINCGARS signals and another one in the 225 to 400 MHz band for non-frequency hopping line-of-sight signals. Both multicouplers can serve to transmit or receive four signals on one antenna simultaneously. Because of electromagnetic interference there is typically a required minimum frequency separation between the input signals.

No multicoupler in the Navy can currently deal with more than one frequency-hopping signal on an antenna in the 225 to 400 MHz band. Multicouplers to serve this role are fraught with difficulty and beset by interference from intermodulation products. One model is currently under development.

The Navy currently uses the same antenna for transmission and reception of most signals in the VHF/UHF band. Since there is not 30 dB attenuation typical of spatial isolation, the difficulty is that much greater than if different antennas were used. The 30 dB of spatial isolation is often achieved by shielding or by placing each antenna in the null of the radiation pattern of the other.

One approach to mitigating the interference of the transmitter antenna at the receiving antenna is to tap off some of the energy, change its phase, and add it to the received signal. Such a method of interference cancellation typically does not cancel all of the broad band noise. Multi-path

effects also limit its effectiveness. Such methods as part of the distribution system can do much to allow an increase in the number of signals input to each antenna.

THE CHALLENGE

The JTRS ORD provides for the capability of transmitting or receiving multiple frequency-hopping signals in the 2 MHz to 2.5 GHz band. To accommodate such a requirement while reducing the number of antennas puts a severe strain on the signal distribution system. Increasing the communications capability requires increasing both the number of signals and the bandwidth of each. Since the total spectrum is limited, the frequency separation between each signal must decrease. The challenge is to mitigate the EMI enough that all of the competing goals can be met. Each of the seven types of EMI must be mitigated for multiple frequency-hopping transmitters to be used.

The distribution system is the arena where these challenges must be met. The distribution system must accommodate frequency-hopping systems over an extremely large range while filtering and isolating each signal. The distribution system must also mitigate the interference of the transmitted signals on the receiver to avoid saturation and desensitization. The distribution system must also accommodate many signals that are closely spaced in frequency. The need to reduce topside crowding and weight prevents using many antennas.

Solving the problem of decreasing the EMI will take the concerted efforts of government and private industry. The rapid development of mobile communications in the past decade has provided a vivid picture of what this cooperation can do. The development of sophisticated orthogonal codes for multiple simultaneous users is an example.

CONCLUSION

The ORD of the JTRS requires new ways of thinking on the role of shipboard communications. There should be consideration of the entire communications system. The individual components must accommodate a large range of frequency. These components

must have an open architecture so that other companies can bid for replacing and upgrading the equipment. In particular, the distribution system must mitigate the seven sources of EMI so that each antenna can accommodate multiple signals. Only then will the superstructure of a ship have a significantly reduced weight, moment, and radar cross section for increased speed and storage of mission-critical supplies. The Navy must have this capability to meet the needs of twenty-first century missions.